

Investigating Height-Dependent Energy Losses and Transfer Asymmetry in Vertically Repelling Neodymium Magnet Systems

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Abstract

When a neodymium magnet is dropped onto a repelling magnet, energy transfers between gravitational potential energy and stored magnetic field energy are accompanied by dissipative losses from air resistance, friction, and magnetic hysteresis. This investigation quantified these losses to determine whether energy transfer efficiency depends on initial drop height and whether downward and upward conversions exhibit symmetry.

Two efficiency ratios were defined: $r(\text{down})$ (gravitational-to-magnetic conversion efficiency) and $r(\text{rebound})$ (magnetic-to-gravitational conversion efficiency). A preliminary force-displacement experiment established an empirical function for stored magnetic energy by fitting measured repulsion forces to Coulomb's inverse-square law ($R^2=0.966$). The primary experiment measured initial drop heights (14.5-31.5 cm), minimum approach distances, and rebound heights across three trials per height using 240fps slow-motion video analysis.

Results revealed significant asymmetry where $r(\text{rebound})$ averaged 0.862 compared to $r(\text{down})$'s 0.568, indicating substantially higher efficiency during magnetic-to-gravitational conversion. Both ratios showed weak positive correlation with drop height (gradients 0.00519 and 0.00983 respectively), suggesting minor velocity-dependent losses beyond constant friction. The $r(\text{down})$ showed stronger height dependence ($R^2=0.871$) than $r(\text{rebound})$ ($R^2=0.323$), consistent with higher descent velocities amplifying air resistance effects.

This asymmetry likely arises from magnetic hysteresis preferentially dissipating energy during field compression and velocity-dependent eddy current losses being greater during faster downward motion. These findings demonstrate that energy transfer in magnetic suspension systems is fundamentally asymmetric, with implications for optimizing efficiency in magnetic levitation and energy harvesting applications where minimizing hysteretic losses is critical.

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1. Research Design

1.1 Introduction

This investigation explores how energy is dissipated in a system of vertically aligned neodymium magnets. When a magnet is dropped above a repelling magnet, gravitational potential energy is converted into magnetic potential energy and then back into gravitational potential energy as it rebounds. Not all energy is recovered, due to friction, air resistance, and intrinsic magnetic losses such as hysteresis and eddy currents. The aim of this experiment is to quantify these losses, assess whether they depend on the initial drop height, and determine if energy transfer efficiency is symmetric between downward and upward motion. The findings of this study could be interesting or applicable to magnetic suspension systems, or trains or other energy capture systems, where understanding energy loss is crucial for fine-tuning or optimizing efficiency. This paper explores this concept by calculating stored energy between initial, lowest and rebound stages of the magnetic drop, a coefficient of energy transfer efficiency is found.

1.2 Research Question

*To what extent do **energy losses** (quantified through r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$) during the transfer between gravitational potential energy (GPE) and magnetic potential energy (MPE) in a vertically dropped neodymium magnet depend on the **initial drop height**, and how symmetric are these losses between downward and upward motion?*

1.3 Modelling

Figure 1: Diagram of magnet drop and stages of the rebound. (1) initial height, (2) maximum stored magnetic energy, (3) rebound. (self-designed with Google Diagrams)

We represent the energy changes during the dropping process with the following model:

$$\text{Initial GPE (1)} \rightarrow \text{KE} \rightarrow \text{Magnetic Potential Energy (2)} \rightarrow \text{KE} \rightarrow \text{Final GPE (3)}$$

Stage 1: All energy in the system is gravitational potential (GPE)

Stage 1 to 2: GPE is converted into kinetic energy (KE), then captured as stored magnetic energy (referred to as MPE in this paper)

Stage 2: KE is zero and the recoverable energy henceforth is the current MPE

Stage 2 to 3: Stored MPE converts to KE as it accelerates the magnet

Step 3: At the apex of the rebound, as KE is zero, and the energy recovered is the GPE at the rebound height

For the experiment, r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$ are measures of how much energy is retained as a portion of the energy present in stage 1 and stage 2, respectively. To be more precise, r_{down} quantifies energy loss from stage 1 to 2 ($GPE \rightarrow MPE$) and the $r_{rebound}$ from stage 2 to 3 ($GPE \rightarrow MPE$). These metrics only consider what portion of the recoverable energy was recovered (defined more rigorously in section 2.3), as opposed to a fraction of the total energy in the system at either stage. The formulas are defined here (Section 2.4 goes into more detail on how they were derived):

$$r_{down} = \frac{E_{recovered,lowest}}{E_{recoverable,initial}} = \frac{MPE(h_{lowest})}{GPE(h_{initial}) - GPE(h_{lowest})}$$

$$r_{rebound} = \frac{E_{recovered,rebound}}{E_{recoverable,lowest}} = \frac{GPE(h_{rebound}) - GPE(h_{lowest})}{MPE(h_{lowest}) - MPE(h_{rebound})}$$

In the study, energy loss—through tube friction, air resistance, magnetic hysteresis or internal eddy currents—is analysed on both downwards and upwards stages, involving the change from GPE to MPE (downwards) and MPE to GPE (upwards;rebound). Thus, to meaningfully separate and quantify the amount of energy lost between downwards and upwards motions for the purpose of better modelling and understanding the energy transfer process, calculating the amount of magnetic potential energy (MPE) stored in the intermediate stage of the system when the magnet is at its closest approach to the repelling magnet (velocity will also be zero) is essential to separate downwards and upwards energy losses.

When repelling magnetic fields are pushed into each other, they act similarly to a spring, however the force isn't directly proportional to distance. Rather, the repulsion force between two magnets follows Coulomb's law of magnetic force, defined as:

$$F(d) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \times \frac{m_1 \times m_2}{d^2}$$

Where:

μ_0 is the permeability constant of free space ($4\pi \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ H/m}$)

m_1 and m_2 are strengths of the magnetic fields

d is the distance between the centers of magnetic fields

Integrating this function w.r.t distance yields the stored energy within the system. To model and then integrate $F(d)$ which yields $W(d)$ —The work function for our magnets (we will refer to this as $MPE(d)$ henceforth)—a preliminary experiment is required to find the value of $m_1 \times m_2$ for the set of magnets used in the experiment.

To do this, the amount of force applied directly normal to the center of the opposing magnetic fields and the resulting distance between the centers of both magnets were recorded. Plotting these the points of force against displacement, and using a linear regression to find an experimentally derived value for $m_1 \times m_2$ led to the derivation of our magnets' work function, which represents the potential energy stored within the opposing magnets at a certain distance, crucial for the independent investigation of energy loss during both halves of the entire rebound process.

1.4 Hypothesis

It is hypothesized that the total energy loss during the magnet's motion arises from three primary sources:

1. **Magnetic hysteresis and internal eddy currents:** internal dissipation within the magnet material as magnetic domains are reoriented during compression and release (Graham, 1982).
2. **Tube friction:** friction between the magnet and acrylic guide tube is expected to be largely independent of drop height because the normal force between the magnet and tube remains approximately constant (as the tube walls are parallel to the magnet sides), and thus contributes a fixed energy loss.
3. **Air resistance:** the drag opposing the magnet's motion, which grows roughly with the square of velocity at higher speeds (Dourmashkin, n.d.). At the relatively low velocities used in this experiment, the drag may be approximately linear with velocity, likely being a weak dependence of energy loss on drop height.

Based on these factors, the following predictions are made:

- **Dependence on drop height:** Air resistance and hysteretic losses may grow with velocity (which grows with initial drop height), while friction remains constant. Consequently, r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$ are expected to increase modestly with drop height, reflecting slightly more efficient energy conversion at higher initial energies, though this assumes that air resistance and hysteresis have a large enough impact.

- **Symmetry of energy transfer:** Friction and air resistance act the same on both downward and upward stages, but magnetic hysteresis is expected to disproportionately dissipate energy during compression (Graham, 1982), as the magnetic domains require more work to compress than they return upon release. Therefore, r_{down} (GPE \rightarrow MPE) is predicted to be consistently lower than $r_{rebound}$ (MPE \rightarrow GPE), indicating asymmetry in energy transfer efficiency.

Formally, if $E_{loss, friction} \approx constant$, $E_{loss, air} \approx v^2 \sim h_{drop}$ and $E_{loss, hysteresis} \propto v_{compression}$

then $r_{down} < r_{rebound}$, and $r_{down}, r_{rebound}$ weakly increase with drop height

1.5 Variables

1.5.1 Control Variables

Control Variables		
Control Variable	How it was Controlled	Why it Needs to be Controlled
Magnets and Orientation	The same pair of neodymium magnets was used throughout, with polarity kept constant (north facing downwards, south upwards).	Ensures consistency in magnetic field strength and interaction; reversing polarity or changing magnets would alter the repulsive force and energy transfer.
Acrylic Cylinder	A single clear acrylic tube of uniform diameter and wall thickness was used.	Ensures constant frictional effects and prevents eddy currents (which would occur in conductive materials and alter the magnet's velocity).
Release Time and	Magnet was held in place	Prevents variation in initial

Method	using a magnetic clip and released with a quick, consistent jolt to minimize sideways motion.	velocity or tilt, ensuring consistent initial conditions for each drop.
Camera, Ruler, and Tube Positioning	The ruler was fixed parallel to the tube, and the camera was mounted at a fixed height and distance perpendicular to the setup.	Keeps parallax error and measurement scaling constant across trials, ensuring rebound height measurements are comparable.
Lighting Conditions	All trials were performed under the same indoor lighting setup, with no direct sunlight or reflections on the acrylic tube.	Prevents changes in video clarity or contrast, allowing accurate height tracking frame by frame.
Gravitational Acceleration Constant	Conducted in the same location under uniform local gravitational conditions.	Ensures that changes in rebound height are due to magnetic and dissipative effects, not variations in gravitational acceleration. (9.81 m s^{-2} used.) (Redondo, n.d.)

1.5.2 Independent and Dependant Variables

Description	Units	Instrument / Method	Uncertainty	Justification / Range
Dependant Variable				
Initial drop height of the magnet	cm	Measured with a ruler mounted alongside the tube, level view to minimize parallax. Always measured as the vertical distance between	$\pm 0.1 \text{ cm}$	Heights from 14.5 cm to 31.5 cm with 1cm increments were chosen to cover a range that produces measurable bounces while avoiding magnet collisions that could damage the apparatus or cause unsafe forces. Moreover at 14.5 cm and above, MPE is negligible, which makes it possible to assume that all the energy in the system is in GPE initially. This makes calculations simpler. 1cm increments gave

		magnet centers		enough data points between 14.5 cm and 31.5 cm for a conclusive analysis.
Independent Variable				
Rebound height of the magnet after hitting the repelling magnet	cm	Measured with the same ruler, recorded via video frame-by-frame for accuracy	± 0.2 cm (from video/video frame resolution and parallax)	Rebound height reflects the energy retained after losses, directly allowing calculation of energy loss (GPE difference). Measuring in cm ensures consistency with initial height measurements.
Lowest height of the magnet during drop	cm	Always measured as the vertical distance between magnet centers		Lowest height allows the calculation of energy stored in the magnetic field, to quantify energy loss and capture efficiency during the downwards stage. Measuring in cm ensures consistency with initial height measurements.

1.6 Equipment and Experimental Setup

- 30cm ruler (± 0.05 cm)
- 2 permanent neodymium magnets
- 40cm Acrylic tube
- Metal clamp (to support and hold up ruler and acrylic tube)
- String attached to metallic paper binder (used to hold magnet in place at specific height, and allows for a drop by snagging the metal clip away)
- High speed camera (240fps slo-mo mode, Apple iPhone 13)
- Analytical balance ($\pm 0.005g$)—to measure the mass of the magnet

Figure 2: Experimental setup diagram. (self designed with google drawings)

To maintain experimental rigour and ensure systemic errors were minimized, the rules and acrylic tube were placed as vertically as possible using a digital leveller. Additionally, the camera was placed horizontally and level, and at a height such that key measurements were taken close to the center of the frame to reduce the inaccuracy of measurements at the camera's edge where there is distortion or a perspective that isn't level. Likewise, when setting the magnet to a drop height, the magnet and ruler were viewed straight on.

The ruler measurements were all scaled relative to the center of the bottom magnet, making this point the fixed zero reference for both gravitational and magnetic potential energy calculations. This ensured that all measured heights directly corresponded to the centre-to-centre separation between magnets, allowing

consistent comparison across trials and accurate computation of energy changes during descent and rebound.

The setup for the preliminary experiment was as follows:

Figure 3: Preliminary experimental setup diagram. (self designed with google drawings)

In addition to the other equipment, the preliminary experiment required:

- Cylindrical brass calibration weights of 50 g and 100 g

1.7 Procedure and Methodology

All heights and distances were calculated using a 30cm ruler, positioned directly vertical and parallel to the acrylic tube. Heights were measured as the distance between the centers of both magnets.

1.7.2 Primary Experiment Procedure

For each height drop, 3 repeats were conducted. Doing 3 repeats struck a balance between error minimization and experiment practicality. In each repeat, the following steps and procedure were used:

1. Position the magnet at the initial drop height by sliding the metallic paper binder along the outside of the acrylic tube. View the ruler level to avoid parallax error.
2. Begin recording in slow motion
3. Give a fast tug on the metallic paper binder holding the magnet in place, causing it to go into freefall. Do this perpendicular to the acrylic tube to ensure the clip doesn't impart any additional velocity to the magnet.
4. After the magnet rebounds once, the recording can be stopped.
5. Observe and record the initial drop height, distance of closest approach to opposing magnet and maximum rebound height from the slow motion footage. Do this frame by frame to identify the points where the magnet had approximately no velocity.
6. Scale heights recorded on ruler such that heights measured are the distance between magnet centers (from the distance between the two magnet surfaces facing each other, add the height of the magnet 2.6 cm to get the center distances).

1.7.2 Preliminary Procedure

To conduct the preliminary experiment, which compared force applied and distance between magnet centers, the following procedure was used for each weight measured.

1. Place the non-magnetic weight on the magnet gently
2. Gently vibrate and knock on the tube until the magnet and weight settles at a stable height and doesn't move down further with continued vibration.
3. Record the weight (including magnet) and distance between the magnet centers, by viewing the ruler straight on.
4. After removing the weight, restore the magnet to a higher position, then repeat the process for each weight.

Measuring the mass of the magnet itself was challenging because it would interfere with the measurement of the analytical mass balance and pull on the metal base plate of the scale. To fix this, the magnet first was placed at different vertical distances to the scale, and the height at which the magnet began to cause interference was observed. Next, the magnet was placed on top of a sufficiently tall styrofoam box such that it wouldn't interfere with the scale. The scale was tared with the styrofoam box, before placing the magnet on top. The mass of the magnet was then recorded.

1.8 Risk Assessment

Consideration Type	Significance
Safety	An acrylic tube was used instead of glass to avoid the risk of shattering or sharp broken glass
	Neodymium magnets are very strong and can snap together with enough force to pinch fingers or shatter. To prevent injury, magnets were handled with non-metallic tools and gloves, kept at least far apart except during measurements, and moved one at a time (Eclipse Magnetics, n.d.) The acrylic tube served as a barrier, containing sudden movements and preventing contact. Metallic objects and electronics were kept away, and eye protection was worn throughout to guard against

	possible fragments or impacts. Opposing sides of the magnet were clearly marked with permanent markers to ensure that attracting sides weren't accidentally placed together.
Ethical	This investigation did not raise any significant ethical concerns, as it involved only inanimate materials, with no living subjects or personal data.
Environmental	Environmental impact was minimal, since the experiment required only small, reusable components and produced no waste, emissions, or chemical by-products. All materials were reused or stored safely for future experiments, ensuring negligible ecological effect.

2. Data Analysis

2.1 Preliminary Experiment

Distance (m) ± 0.0005 m	Force applied (N) ± 0.005 N
0.097	0.91
0.095	1.43
0.085	1.93
0.079	2.43
0.075	2.93
0.07	3.43
0.067	3.93
0.065	4.43
0.062	4.93
0.06	5.43
0.059	5.93
0.055	6.43
0.05	6.93

Table 1: Raw data of Distance between magnet centers (m) and Force applied (N)

Figure 4: Graph of force applied to distance between magnet centers.

Preliminary experiments were conducted to determine the work function of the magnets, providing an estimate of the magnetic potential energy stored within the system. Figure 4 displays the force applied vertically downwards (including the magnet's own weight) to the top magnet as a function of the distance between the two magnetic centers. The measurement uncertainties were considered negligible. Theoretically, the Coulomb-like dipole model predicts an inverse-square relationship between force and distance. When fitted to the data with a regression, the empirical relationship $F(d) = \frac{m}{d^2} + c$, with values $m = 0.0219688$ and $c = -0.993919$ was found to best describe the measurements, achieving an R^2 value of 0.966. The inclusion of the constant c improves the accuracy of the fit and likely accounts for

systematic effects such as minor measurement errors, potentially of center magnet poles, and additional small forces present in the experimental setup, such as the slightly off center additional mass. The parameter m represents the effective magnetic strength governing the repulsive interaction ($m = \frac{\mu_0 \times m_1 \times m_2}{4\pi}$), while c acts as a correction term that ensures the model remains valid within the measured range.

To model the magnetic potential energy, the empirical relationship $F(d) = \frac{m}{d^2} + c$ was integrated with respect to distance. The neutral point (where the stored magnetic energy is zero) is at the x-intercept of the fitted curve:

$$0 = \frac{m}{d_0^2} + c \Rightarrow d_0 = \sqrt{\frac{m}{-c}} \Rightarrow d_0 = 0.1486714$$

$$\text{neutral distance} = 0.1486714 \text{ m} = 14.86714 \text{ cm}$$

As the magnets are brought closer together from this point, work is done against the magnetic repulsion, resulting in energy storage within the magnetic field. Because any distance past the threshold d_0 should have no magnetic influence, but the function produces negative past the threshold, we use add a piecewise condition such that the function range is always positive:

$$F(d) = \left\{ h \leq h_0: \frac{m}{d^2} + c, h > h_0: 0 \right\}$$

Next, to derive the work done function for the magnetic field, we integrate force over distance.

$$MPE(d) = - \int F(d) dd = - \int (\frac{m}{d^2} + c) dd$$

$$MPE(d) = - [-\frac{m}{d} + cd] + C$$

$$MPE(d) = \frac{m}{d} - cd + C$$

When $d > d_0$, we want $MPE(d) = 0$, therefore the final equation is:

$$MPE(h) = \{h \leq h_0: \frac{m}{h} - ch, h > h_0: 0\}.$$

Where $m = 0.0219688$, $c = -0.993919$ and $h_0 = \sqrt{\frac{m}{-c}} \approx 0.148671$ and h_0 and h are in meters. This formulation allows direct computation of magnetic potential energy for each measured displacement (distance between magnet centers) for calculation of energy transfer efficiency ratios between GPE and MPE in the primary experiment.

2.2 Raw Data and Collection

The recorded lowest point and rebound height were averaged across 3 trials and the averages (mean) were plotted against the initial drop height. A table of the collected raw data is shown in Table 2.

Drop height (±0.1 cm)	Lowest point (±0.2 cm)			Bounce height (±0.2 cm)		
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3
14.5	10.5	10.5	10.4	10.5	10.4	10.4
15.5	9.8	9.9	9.8	10.2	10.1	10.3
16.5	9.5	9.6	9.4	10.6	10.5	10.7
17.5	9.1	8.9	9.0	11.5	11.7	11.6
18.5	8.7	8.8	8.6	12.0	11.9	12.1
19.5	8.1	8.2	8.3	12.7	12.7	12.5
20.5	7.9	8.0	8.0	13.2	13.4	13.2
21.5	7.5	7.6	7.4	15.4	14.4	14.2

22.5	7.5	7.3	7.2	14.4	15.4	15.5
23.5	6.9	7.0	7.0	16.0	15.6	15.4
24.5	6.7	6.4	7.0	16.8	17.1	15.4
25.5	6.6	6.9	6.9	16.0	16.1	16.3
26.5	6.4	6.4	6.5	16.5	17.0	17.4
27.5	6.1	6.2	6.3	18.7	18.5	18.1
28.5	6.0	6.0	6.2	18.7	19.0	18.5
29.5	5.9	6.0	5.9	18.5	18.3	18.9
30.5	6.0	5.8	5.7	19.5	20.0	19.5
31.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	19.5	20.8	21.2

Table 2: Unprocessed data, with data of from each of the three repeats at each drop

height (14.5 – 31.5 cm)

Qualitative Observations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When the magnet was rising, at times it would rattle or catch slightly on the sides of the acrylic tube • The magnet had a slight angle and didn't fit perfectly upright within the tube

Table 3: Qualitative observations

2.3 Uncertainties

Measurement	Uncertainty
Initial drop height	± 0.1 cm
Lowest height	± 0.2 cm
Rebound	± 0.2 cm
Magnet Mass	± 0.005 g (negligible)
MPE model	± 3.4 % (from preliminary uncertainty in R^2 value)

Table 4: Uncertainties

2.4 Data Processing

First the averages for height measurements (lowest height and rebound height) were calculated like so:

$$h_{average} = \frac{1}{3}h_1 + \frac{1}{3}h_2 + \frac{1}{3}h_3$$

Next to find energy loss coefficients, r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$ for each drop height finding the total energy of the system at lowest and rebound heights must be calculated first. The magnet mass was measured to be 92.99g, this value (converted to kilograms) was used for all gravitation potential energy (GPE) calculations (where h is also in meters):

$$GPE(h) = 0.09299 \times 9.81 \times h$$

Stored magnetic energy (MPE) was calculated as function of height from the centers of magnets, using the function derived in section 2.1:

$$MPE(h) = \left\{ h \leq h_0: \frac{m}{h} - ch, h > h_0: 0 \right\}$$

Where $m = 0.0219688$, $c = -0.993919$ and $h_0 = \sqrt{\frac{m}{-c}} \approx 0.1487$ and h_0 and h are in meters. Additionally, because all points recorded in the drop (initial, closest approach and rebound) are stationary, the kinetic energy is zero and not considered.

Calculating r_{down} gives us the fraction of energy retained in the system when the magnet is at its lowest, out of the energy present initially.

The initial energy contained within the system is completely gravitational potential energy, as long as the initial drop height is more than h_0 , which is true for the set of data points in the experiment.

$$E_{total,initial} = GPE(h_{initial})$$

At the lowest point, the energy is primarily captured in the magnetic field, stored as MPE with a small remainder still as GPE:

$$E_{total,lowest} = GPE(h_{lowest}) + MPE(h_{lowest})$$

Meaning that $E_{recoverable,initial} = GPE(h_{initial}) - GPE(h_{lowest})$

And $E_{recovered,lowest} = MPE(h_{lowest})$

Therefore, r_{down} is:

$$r_{down} = \frac{E_{recovered,lowest}}{E_{recoverable,initial}} = \frac{MPE(h_{lowest})}{GPE(h_{initial}) - GPE(h_{lowest})}$$

This denominator represents the amount of gravitational energy that was available to convert—the difference between the initial GPE and the GPE at the lowest point.

The numerator is how much of that actually ended up stored magnetically.

At the highest point in the rebound, the system has a total energy of:

$$E_{total,rebound} = MPE(h_{rebound}) + GPE(h_{rebound})$$

Therefore the amount of energy that was is transferred to GPE from MPE is

$$E_{recoverable,lowest} = MPE(h_{lowest}) - MPE(h_{rebound})$$

Subsequently, the amount of energy actually recovered is:

$$E_{recovered,rebound} = GPE(h_{rebound}) - GPE(h_{lowest})$$

Therefore:

$$r_{rebound} = \frac{E_{recovered,rebound}}{E_{recoverable,lowest}} = \frac{GPE(h_{rebound}) - GPE(h_{lowest})}{MPE(h_{lowest}) - MPE(h_{rebound})}$$

This expresses how effectively the magnetic potential energy stored at the lowest point is converted back into GPE.

Drop height (cm)	Initial GPE (J)	Mean lowest height (cm)	GPE (J)	MPE (J)	r, down	Mean rebound height (cm)	GPE (J)	MPE (J)	r, rebound
14.5	0.1323	10.5	0.0955	0.0191	0.5190	10.4	0.0952	0.0194	0.8962
15.5	0.1414	9.8	0.0897	0.0263	0.5091	10.2	0.0930	0.0219	0.7625
16.5	0.1505	9.5	0.0867	0.0308	0.4830	10.6	0.0967	0.0178	0.7681
17.5	0.1596	9.0	0.0821	0.0387	0.4994	11.6	0.1058	0.0099	0.8216
18.5	0.1688	8.7	0.0794	0.0442	0.4939	12.0	0.1095	0.0075	0.8216
19.5	0.1779	8.2	0.0748	0.0546	0.5295	12.6	0.1152	0.0046	0.8096
20.5	0.1870	8.0	0.0727	0.0601	0.5258	13.3	0.1210	0.0026	0.8410
21.5	0.1961	7.5	0.0684	0.0726	0.5687	14.7	0.1338	0.0007	0.9093
22.5	0.2053	7.3	0.0669	0.0776	0.5611	15.1	0.1377	0.0000	0.9126
23.5	0.2144	7.0	0.0636	0.0898	0.5951	15.7	0.1429	0.0000	0.8842
24.5	0.2235	6.7	0.0611	0.0997	0.6137	16.4	0.1499	0.0000	0.8910
25.5	0.2326	6.8	0.0620	0.0958	0.5618	16.1	0.1472	0.0000	0.8885
26.5	0.2417	6.4	0.0587	0.1106	0.6042	17.0	0.1548	0.0000	0.8688
27.5	0.2509	6.2	0.0566	0.1211	0.6234	18.4	0.1682	0.0000	0.9213
28.5	0.2600	6.1	0.0553	0.1276	0.6235	18.7	0.1709	0.0000	0.9056
29.5	0.2691	5.9	0.0541	0.1344	0.6252	18.6	0.1694	0.0000	0.8574
30.5	0.2782	5.8	0.0532	0.1398	0.6211	19.7	0.1794	0.0000	0.9029
31.5	0.2874	5.5	0.0502	0.1593	0.6715	20.5	0.1870	0.0000	0.8591

Table 5: Processed data

2.5 Analysis

Lowest point (cm) and Rebound height (cm) vs. Drop height

Figure 5: Mean bounce height (cm) and Rebound height vs. Drop height (cm)

The averaged lowest-point and rebound heights increased approximately linearly with drop height (with very strong R^2 values of 0.960 and 0.987 for lowest height and rebound height, respectively), indicating proportional energy exchange over the tested range. The shallower gradient for the lowest-point curve reflects the rapid growth of magnetic potential energy as the magnets enter close proximity as also shown by Figure 5.

r , down and r , rebound vs. Drop height (cm)

Figure 6: plot of r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$ vs Drop height (cm).

Analysis of graph in Figure 6 suggests that r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$ are somewhat dependent on drop height, as both lines show a noticeable, yet modest positive correlation (with a gradient of 0.00983 and 0.00519 respectively), which points towards some factor of energy loss during both transfer stages having a quadratic relationship with drop height, as the ratio is not constant. This suggests a slight influence of air resistance or magnetic hysteresis in energy loss, as hypothesized.

The regression line of r_{down} has a much higher value of $R^2 = 0.871$ compared to $r_{rebound}$ value of $R^2 = 0.323$. As values for $r_{rebound}$ also show a moderately higher variation in comparison. This higher variance can likely be explained by the fact that values used in calculation for the rebound were relatively smaller compared to for the initial drop, as rebound height and resulting GPE would be less than the initial drop height, this means that uncertainties in the MPE and GPE function had a larger

relative impact on the values, increasing their random variance. Furthermore, qualitative observations showed the magnet would sometimes shake and rattle while being pushed up, which could cause more random variance in dynamic friction between each drop.

r_{down} shows a slightly steeper gradient than $r_{rebound}$ (9.83×10^{-3} vs 5.19×10^{-3}), which shows more influence from the drop height. Because the down stage has a higher average velocity compared to the rebound stage and air resistance becomes a larger source of energy loss at higher velocities, we expect to see that r_{down} has more influence from factors that grow square to velocity, such as air resistance. On the other hand, the shallower gradient of $r_{rebound}$ shows that the rebound stage has energy losses which are generally more constant, suggesting that friction is the primary loss of energy. This matches observations seen in the graph.

Perhaps most significantly, the average of $r_{rebound}$ is significantly higher than r_{down} being 0.862 compared to 0.568. In the context of the experiment, this suggests that the transfer between GPE to MPE is far less efficient than MPE to GPE. While this is consistent with magnetic hysteresis—where the work required to compress the field exceeds the energy returned during expansion—the magnitude of the difference also points to velocity-dependent resistive forces (air resistance and friction). Since the magnet falls from a greater height than it rebounds to, its average velocity during the descent is higher, leading to greater resistive losses (as $F_{drag} \propto v$) on the way down. Furthermore, the conductive nature of the neodymium magnet means internal eddy currents are theoretically possible. Like air resistance, these currents create a

damping force that opposes motion in both directions (up and down). However, since the magnet's velocity is higher during the descent, the power dissipated by these internal currents ($P \propto v^2$) would be greater on the way down, contributing to the lower efficiency (r_{down}) observed.

3. Conclusion

This investigation set out to determine how the efficiency of energy transfer between gravitational potential energy (GPE) and magnetic potential energy (MPE) depends on the initial drop height of a vertically falling neodymium magnet. By separating the downward and upward stages of motion through the ratios r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$, it became possible to quantify how much energy was retained in each conversion step and to distinguish between the two directions of energy flow.

The results show that both r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$ increase modestly with drop height, implying a weak dependence on initial energy. This suggests that energy losses are not purely constant but contain a small velocity-dependent component—consistent with a minor contribution from air resistance, which grows with the square of velocity. The linear-plus-quadratic trend therefore broadly supports the hypothesis that the system's losses are mostly proportional to the initial energy, with only a small nonlinear term.

Combined with the results analyzed in Section 2.4, these findings support the notion that the efficiency of energy transfer in the system is not symmetrical and dependent

to a small extent on the initial drop height. The consistently higher values of $r_{rebound}$ suggest that a larger proportion of magnetic potential energy (MPE) is successfully converted back into gravitational potential energy (GPE) than the reverse process. This asymmetry likely arises from hysteresis effects within the magnetic domains, which preferentially dissipate energy during compression rather than release or eddy current formation in the magnet material. Additionally, energy loss seems to be dependent on the drop height to some extent, potentially caused by quadratic factors as hypothesized, such as air resistance.

Overall, the data partially supports the initial hypothesis: energy loss scales with drop height, but the assumption of symmetric efficiency between downward and upward energy transfer does not hold. This insight may have implications for technologies relying on magnetic suspension or levitation, where minimizing hysteretic losses is essential for efficiency and stability.

4. Evaluation

The experiment produced clear, consistent trends: both r_{down} and $r_{rebound}$ show modest dependence on drop height, and a reproducible asymmetry ($r_{down} < r_{rebound}$) was observed. The main limitation is that several sources of uncertainty (like the MPE calibration and small measurement biases from video/ruler alignment) propagate non-linearly into r values, increasing scatter and creating potential bias in the magnitude of the ratios. Many of these issues are correctable with straightforward changes to instrumentation and analysis; none invalidate the

qualitative conclusions but they do limit the quantitative precision and the confidence drawn from small slope/curvature effects (e.g. the small quadratic term attributed to air drag).

4.1 Effect of Uncertainties

Both random and systematic uncertainties were present. Random errors mainly arose from reading rebound and minimum heights from slow-motion footage: even though frame-by-frame analysis (240 fps) minimized subjectivity, slight tilt in the magnet or parallax in the ruler alignment could shift height readings by up to ± 0.2 cm, especially at higher speeds where motion blur was non-negligible. Averaging three trials reduced statistical scatter, though uncertainty remained a relatively large portion of the distances measured in the scale of this experiment. The uncertainty for $r_{rebound}$ was particularly high, resulting in a R^2 value of only 0.323, leading to low statistical power in the analysis of dependence to drop height. This very high variance severely limits the ability to draw conclusions from analysis of the rebound stage. More repeats should have been conducted to address this.

Systematic errors were also influential. The calibration of the magnetic potential energy (MPE) function relied on an empirical fit $F(d) = \frac{m}{d^2} + c$; although $R^2 = 0.966$ indicates a strong fit, the presence of the constant c implies that the true relationship may deviate slightly at close separations where magnetic field lines are non-uniform (Zhang et. al., 2020). This could lead to consistent over or underestimation of MPE and subsequent bias in r values. The magnet mass measurement also carried a

small but finite systematic error (± 0.005 g) from the non-magnetic stand method, though its influence on GPE calculations (< 0.01 %) was insignificant.

Finally, small angular misalignments of the magnet within the acrylic tube occasionally altered the apparent center position by up to ~ 0.1 cm and changed the magnetic field angle, causing further noise in measurements.

4.2 Strengths

Strength	Significance
Complete theoretical foundation	Deriving separate models for r values allowed a detailed analysis of magnetic energy exchange in both directions, going beyond a simple rebound ratio.
Effective control of variables	Limiting external influences through many control variables ensured results stayed accurate and increased the conclusiveness of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables.
Preliminary experiment calibration	The preliminary force-distance experiment allowed direct empirical determination of magnetic parameters, giving physical grounding to the MPE model rather than relying purely on theoretical assumptions.
Video-based precision	Using slow-motion capture minimized timing uncertainty and provided reliable, repeatable measurements of turning points, especially vital when distances being measured are small and magnets are in free fall.

4.3 Weaknesses and Limitations

Weakness / Limitation	Effect on Results	Proposed Improvement
The MPE model may not fully capture magnetic field behaviour.	Causes small systematic offset in calculated MPE, biasing both r ratios. However the range of deflections in the MPE model (5–9.7 cm) closely overlap the values in experiment data (5.5–~14.8 cm), meaning the model was most likely still reasonably usable. The constant c had to be added as without that constant term, the model didn't closely match data points, hinting at a systemic error.	Use a model fitted over a broader distance range, with smaller increments between weights. Additionally, using a magnetometer could improve certainty in recording the magnetic field strengths.
Slight misalignment of camera and ruler	Introduces parallax, particularly at top and bottom of frame; more prevalent on the higher drops.	Employ a fixed orthogonal camera mount with calibration grid or digital motion-tracking
Limited number of repeats ($n = 3$)	Increases uncertainty of mean rebound height	Increase to 5–7 repeats to better constrain random error
Manual identification of magnet centers	Subjective and potentially inconsistent, especially for blurred frames, tilted magnets and non-orthogonal camera angles.	Use computer measurement tools to find center automatically
Neglect of rotational energy	Minor but systematic underestimation of total energy loss	Record top-down footage to confirm rotational motion is negligible
Acrylic guide tube was too wide	Exacerbates rotational energy losses and makes the magnet rattle and not be perfectly vertical, causing inconsistencies with the magnetic field and friction. The tilt the magnet had also made it difficult at times to estimate the centers	Use tube with a better fitting diameter
Clamp and metal stand was magnetic	Caused potential magnetic interference and systematic errors, especially with the MPE function	Use a plastic clamp, or other

		non-magnetic apparatus
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